

Excellence in Leadership for Transformation

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श्वेत शाहू

**Madan Bhandari
Memorial College**

श्वेत शार्दूल

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Cultivating Research Culture through Unique Exercise of Individual Research Centre

Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D. (QAA Department)

Dear Readers,

I hope many of us are not much interested in research. I am attempting to put forward few ways how researcher inside you can be brought into action through systematic peer relationship. It is important for you as a teacher or student though you work in Nepal where researchers are not getting much attention. It is written through discussion with a panel of experts and scholars across the globe and special assistance from Madan Bhandari Memorial College research scholars and professors. The College has several experts like the research director and many more faculties along with scholars with advanced degrees among whom a common topic of discussion is how to develop research culture?

If you teach well, you will be famous among your students only and their friends and associates, however, if you research well, you will be famous everywhere in the globe. You should do research to solve the problem or generate new knowledge to be applicable for solving problems in future. That is why we should judge our research by ourself in terms of solution, attempt to solution or knowledge creation rather than publication only. Many more significance of research is there which you know better than me. In this paper, I just would like to share unique practice of MBMC to promote research here among us.

Individual Research Centre

Individual person based research centre with one focused research topic is tried to be established as the concept has been successfully implemented at Srinivas University, India under Prof. Dr. P. S. Aithal leadership. It focuses to develop area of research in an innovative way through representatives in a collaborative way. Every researcher found to have more than 2 to 5 research areas where scholarly publications are found to be practiced. In Nepal, every scholar is found to involve in 3to10 subjects teaching based on textbooks/ study books. Research should lead to innovation which means multiple use of single expertise as washing machine can be

used for making Mahi / Chhas. Pencil and eraser get combined though both were developed; however, its combination is innovation. It is aimed to perform Incremental Innovation and Radical Innovation though Disruptive Innovation may be welcomed if it comes. Being an academicians we should focus literature based research which gives only incremental or radical innovation, not disruptive.

We at MBMC encourage to express Area of Employment of professional teachers who are involved as part-time faculty to share Problems and Solutions of respective field along with Present model and new model possibility. Application of specialization subject or teaching subject in the society might be focused through it as possible research topic highlighting new technology and applications in concerned subject/area along with historical information and their relevancy in present and future days. We focus to assess present problems and opportunities in society, industries and organizations for identifying the needs of resource innovation and management best practices and innovations to ease the lifestyle in scientific and systematic predictions in everyone's area of expertise. Observation, literature reviews, professional conferences and experts are few sources to generate research. New models and new analysis as topic after which state that problem clearly and completely to determine the feasibility of the research breaking into Identify sub problems as completely researchable units as small as possible in number adding up to the total problem which must be clearly tied to the interpretation of the data and we express it through our Individual Research Center for following reasons:

- Crystalizing your research idea in a systematic way
- Thinking critically, creatively, & Out of the Box
- Deep and Focused thinking on a problem or Topic
- Identifying Problems & Synthesizing possible solutions

- Analysing individual solutions from different perspectives
- Selecting Optimum solution
- Implementation of Optimum solution
- Extension of Research idea into Mega Project
- The center may provide Advisor/ Committee members/ colleagues
- It may provide Reading literature/publications through its own Library/internet followed by Conferences/seminars for more and more opportunity for research.
- Draw inspiration from anywhere you can and validate in your small likeminded expert group.
- Rational thinking, Creative thinking, Searching the literature, Scanning the media, rainstorming, Relevance Trees, Exploring past projects, Discussion, Keeping an ideas notebook would become your habit if you do its practice making it easy to generate research interest.

The continuous academic discourses conducted at MBMC might be the best option to generate valid research topics.

Structure of Individual Research Centre

A general structure could be expressed in given points:

- **Area of IRC:** The area of research should be expressed.
- **Name of IRC:** Name of topic may be name of IRC in broad sense.

Table 1. Research Matrix

SN	Objective	Data Required	Data Collection Tool	Data Analysis	Expected Outcome
1.					
2.					

We want every individual research center to prepare a brief concept to discuss their idea as given format. I also use it to track students projects under my supervisions regularly.

Proposed Title

Proposal Technical Details

1. Summary of Proposal (500 words)
2. Objectives (200 words)
3. Review of Literature (National and International Level (200 words)
 - a) National Level
 - b) International Level
4. Work Plan (400 words)
5. Methodology (200 words)
6. Expected Deliverables (200 words)

- Photo, Name, Address of Coordinator including ORCID-ID, & E-Mail- ID.
- **Description of IRC:** About identified Research Topic, Definition, Features, Challenges along with Opportunities to inspire individuals to collaborate in your team.
- **Objectives of IRC:**
- **Expected Outcome:** Based on Objectives what is your expectation from Research?
- **Working Papers:** List 2-4 proposed Papers to be published in Proceedings of Journals based on Objectives of the ARC
- **List of Collaborators:** it may have 0 to 10 People which may consists of U.G. Students (4/6), P.G. Students (2 / 4), Faculty Members as Colleague, External institutional Collaborators/ Partners (National & Foreign) and Research Guides (Guide & Co-guide)
- **Publications:** we decide on referencing before going in deep to choose from MLA–Modern Language Association, APA–American Psychological Association, Chicago–, Harvard–, Vancouver–Health Science and IEEE–Engineering Science. We use zotero so its reference management is not an issue here. We always express as research matrix given in table 1.

7. Field of Experience (Keywords)
8. Financial Details
 - Some Hot Issues for research of your interest may be as follow.
 - One Country – One Library (Book, Magazines, & Journals)

We want every individual research center to prepare a brief concept to discuss their idea as given format. I also use it to track students projects under my supervisions regularly.

Proposal Technical Details

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- a) National Level
- b) International Level
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5. Methodology (200 words)
6. Expected Deliverables (200 words)
7. Field of Experience (Keywords)
8. Financial Details
 - Some Hot Issues for research of your interest may be as follow.
 - One Country – One Library (Book, Magazines, & Journals)
 - Education Loan without Interest
 - Compulsory Research Components in UG & PG Curriculum
 - Effective Use of Retired Professionals/ Professors for Nation Building
 - Hot Research Issues in Various Industries: Smart Agriculture,
 - UN Sustainable Development Goals (17),
 - Emerging Technologies & their Impact on Society/Industries etc.

We are strict to the minimum standard to submit a paper for publication as given below:

- Open Access Journal with ISSN where Article should be freely Accessible to Readers
- Copyright should be with Authors. Only publication rights can be given to publishers
- No or zero Article Processing Charges (APC)
- Article should have DOI preferably Cross Ref or DOI Foundation to fetch any citations to the published article
- Submitted Article should be reviewed for originality, novelty, scholarly format, plagiarism, grammar mistakes, citation-reference matching
- The published article should be available for Google Scholar search directly from the Journal immediately after publication

We advised to go to current Issue (in its website) of the Journal for its suitability for publication. Copy the last published article title along with its authors name. Paste it into the “Google scholar search page” and if the paper is available for search and connects to its published

Journal page, then only submit the Article. One of my friends argued with evidence that many journals do not have ISSN also though they are accepted all over the world like Harvard Business Review, which has no ISSN also which encouraged me to support my argument by saying, “think from top, not from bottom.” Only commercial journals who want to make profit should think about accreditation. Other Journals like Journal of Productive Discourse (ProD)

are free publication model like God created free air and water, need no accreditation. Further I assure that Journal doesn't mean Indexing. And Indexing doesn't mean SCI or Scopus. There are many Journals included in UGC care and Scopus totally casual and profit-making one. In the meanwhile, I focus on what is published, not where it is published? Even I want you to apply for patent or copyright if you are really inventing. I want to draw attention of university and university grant commission on <https://telescoper.wordpress.com/2023/03/08/the-cost-of-elsevier/> where a huge amount found to be lost in terms publication charge. That is why regulatory authority should focus on what is published, not where it is published and enhance practice of copyright and patent in carrier development and selection of faculties to save money effectively along quality research. The publication of 21st century focuses on modular publication rather than just traditional mode. You can publish even small part of your research if it is new and apply for intellectual property rights. You may visit <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-023-00861-0>. Let's present a review tips to develop your class note as review paper.

Some common tips for improving literature review:

- **No General at Start:** Give the gist or main theme at start.
- **Importance of Topic:** Highlight importance of topic in your review.
- **Findings v/s Others:** During review differentiate findings and others systematically.
- **Avoid nonspecific citations:** Cite specific with details facts without overlapping.
- **In consistence Findings:** Some time we put different findings together which may misled should be avoided.
- **Paraphrase:** Paraphrasing is most and highlights one issue in one paragraph through continuous change of paragraph.
- **Strong Verb:** Use different strong verbs to show what is done in the perspective research.
- **Meaningful Review:** include only those reviews which may be useful for further discussion.
- **Quotation:** Avoid quotation if possible which may not be possible in language.
- **Framework:** Develop framework based on review.
- **Funneling:** Try to review from broad perspective and concise to the thematic point. You may consider geographical review along with time line such as literature from develops country to developing country including your location based study literature from theoretical to empirical review in specified way.

- **Variable Based:** Review each variable along details methodology to support your methods, framework and findings.
- **Summary Table:** you may adopt Narrative, Systematic, Meta-Analysis, Meta Synthesis, and Argumentative, integrative, historical, methodological or theoretical approach during expressing the summary of table in text.
- **Research Methods:** Never forget to review methodology.

Let us present a review format modified from Srinivas Publication which you may do self-publication also using any of described methods:

1. <https://www.teamscopeapp.com/blog/6-repositories-to-share-your-research-dat>.
2. ORCID-ID,
3. Google Scholar,

4. Research Gate,
5. Elsevier's SSRN,
6. Microsofts Academic, cwww.semanticscholar.org and
7. BASE

It may make your job easy to develop network for learning and research. Expert Cooperation, Student Exchange and Scholarship may be obtained using Research Collaboration and so on. Madan Bhandari Memorial College (Affiliated to Tribhuvan University) Rankings - AD Scientific Index 2023 is 13th based on h-index followed by 9th rank based on Last 6 years i10 index out of 41 Nepal based University/Institution Rankings for 2023 <https://www.adscientificindex.com/university/>

Review Paper Format to Select Research Topic

First Author Name¹ & Last Author Name²

¹First Author affiliation

ORCID-ID: xxxx xxxx xxxx; E-mail: xxxxxxxx

²First Author affiliation

ORCID-ID: xxxx xxxx xxxx;

E-mail: xxxxxxxx

Purpose: Why this paper and what is done here?

Design/Methodology/Approach: Express your review methods with logics and evidence of your approach. Results/ Findings: What are expressed findings, what are your new inferences and contradictions or themes found? Originality/Value: what value is generated through the review?

Type of Paper: Experimental/Empirical/ Exploratory/Literature Review/ Case Study/ Research Analysis, etc.

Keywords: Give 4 to 6 Keywords specific to the research area. At least 2 keywords should be from Title of the Paper.

Table 2: Review of Methodology

	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3	Author 4
Sample size	N/n	N/n	N/n	N/n
Participants	Employees of banks	Employees of MMC	Employees of manufacturing firms	Faculties of higher education institutes
Sampling technique	Random	Stratified	Quota	Purposive
Philosophy of Research	Pragmatic	Constructivism	Positivism	Post-constructivism
Tools for data collection	Structured interview	Structured questionnaire	Face to face fill up of questionnaire	Questionnaire through mail

1. **INTRODUCTION:** Discussion of the research area (Topic & subtopics with 5 to 10 citations)
2. **OBJECTIVES OF REVIEW PAPER:** (All objectives given here should be fulfilled in the paper)
3. **METHODOLOGY:** (of Data & Information collection and Analysis)

The technique has been also suggested by Prof. Dr. Dhrub Kumar Gautam as shown in table 2.

	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3	Author 4
Sample size	N/n	N/n	N/n	N/n
Tools for analysis	Factor analysis	Multiple regression	Multiple regression	Cluster analysis
Unite of analysis	Organization	Individual	District-based	national
Coverage	Single industry of a nation of (Nepal)	Cross country of developed nations (.....)	Cross continent	Cross country of least developed nations

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE/ RELATED WORKS:

Descriptive discussion and gist of findings of 10 to 12 papers and one or more tables (as per

Keywords) containing the gist of the total 50 to 60 related topic papers (In discussion form & tabular form on various subtopics together):

Table 3: Scholarly literature on keyword 1

SN	Area & Focus of the Research: RO/RQ/ Hypothesis	Outcome of the Research: Findings	Methods	Variables	Your conclusion/ comments/ views/ critics	Your conclusion/ comments/ views/ critics	Reference with DOI or URL

Describe each keyword in similar pattern using Tables for other suitable keywords also. Provide description of summary of the review as suggested through section of common tips.

5. CURRENT STATUS & NEW RELATED ISSUES: (& Analysis of these Issues)

Description of summary on the current status based on review.

6. IDEAL SOLUTION, DESIRED STATUS & IMPROVEMENTS REQUIRED: (based on current status)

7. RESEARCH GAP: (Difference between current status & Desired Status).

8. RESEARCH AGENDAS BASED ON RESEARCH GAP: (Various anticipated solutions to decrease the gap (May be developed using Focus Group Discussion method)).

9. ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH AGENDAS: (For importance & viability).

10. FINAL RESEARCH PROPOSAL/PROBLEM IN CHOSEN TOPIC: (Your research topic).

11. ABCD ANALYSIS/SLOC/SIX THINKING HATS/ OTHER ANALYSIS OF CHOSEN RESEARCH PROPOSAL: (One or two analysis in the form of SWOC/ ABCD Listing is suggested)

12. SUGGESTIONS TO IMPLEMENT RESEARCH ACTIVITIES ACCORDING TO THE PROPOSAL:

13. LIMITATIONS OF THE PROPOSAL: (Optional)

14. CONCLUSION: (Conclude by keeping the Objectives of the paper in mind. Argue that all Objectives listed are fulfilled along with summary of result, mentioning of originality/ value added/ Novelty of this research work).

REFERENCES: (Strictly in any specified format with Google scholar hyperlink & DOI hyperlink)

For example:

1. Mishra, A. K. (2022). Teaching and Research Operation at Pokhara University. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7045640>
2. Mishra AK. What is the Best Journal to Publish your Scholarly Article? J Adv Res Const Urban Arch 2021; 6(4): 31-33 (Vancouver)
3. A. K. Mishra & Nepal Ananda, "Be Prepared for Futuristic Sustainable Academic Operation", 9th International Conference on Modern Education and New Learning Technologies, ISBN Number: 978-920-5-20233-4, Page Number 63-67, December, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7748843>

Conclusions and Suggestions: Research culture can be effectively cultivated through unique individual research center. Research should not be limited to publication, but solution to problem or new knowledge. What is published should be given priority over where it is published. Class note should be developed as review based paper. You can adopt 21st century publication model and apply for intellectual property rights. The research matrix, self-publication, modular publication may be helpful for research and future form of publications. ORCID-ID, Google Scholar, Research Gate, Elsevier's SSRN, Microsofts Academic, www.semanticscholar.org. and BASE may make your job easy to develop network. Ranking of MBMC should be raised within top ten higher education institute of Nepal through the continuity of unique exercise.

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